

MAJOR PAPER**LAST NAME: GITUMA****FIRST NAME: CHRISTINE NKIROTE****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote references (with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2023 on Windows 11 Enterprise)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The process of academic essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 7-8)
2. Structure of academic essays (EUCLID 2024, 7-8)
3. Punctuations and language variants (EUCLID 2024, 15-23; 24-32)
4. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
- 6. Style guides (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)**

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have reviewed the content shared in the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack by the International Faculty Coordinator, Professor Laurent Cleenewerck, and Course Instructor, Dr. Kabiru Gulma, which is very comprehensive, including the ACA-401D basic tutorial video delivered by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck. The basic tutorial on the English language and citation styles on how to better package academic essays, which is different from personal writing, has been very insightful. It has provided me with the guidance required to undertake comprehensive research, the required writing style and expectations, and the dos and don'ts. Joining this course aligns with my educational aspirations. From a young age, and being a smart child in class, I had always wanted to further my studies to the highest degree available.

I began with a Bachelor of Science in Information Technology, then undertook a Certificate in International Law and Contemporary Challenges. By then, I had already been working with the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), the UN Refugee agency. I began my career at the Branch office in Nairobi, Kenya, in 2007 before relocating to the Dadaab Refugee Camp in 2008. At that time, the Dadaab refugee camp

was termed the largest camp in the world as it hosted more than 463,000 refugees and asylum seekers (UNHCR 2012). In 2011, I applied for a position as a Resettlement Assistant at the branch office in Kenya. This led to my move back to Nairobi. As the years progressed, I moved from one department to the next, and my career progressed. This led me to realize I needed to enhance my knowledge in Project Management as I began managing projects that required resource mobilization. This led to me applying to undertake a master's in project planning and management in 2013, and in 2019, I opted to undertake a second master's in international Humanitarian Affairs as my work required understanding regional issues related to humanitarian affairs, international humanitarian and human rights law, refugee law, and other legal instruments as this would underpin my experience in refugee protection and management. Through this course, I have been able to progress significantly in my career and catapult myself to the next level. The decision to apply to this Ph.D., which I believe will further propel me to the next level in my career and enhance my knowledge of various issues related to Diplomacy and International Affairs, bearing in mind the exposure my career has availed and the need to work with different governments, stakeholders, and the larger humanitarian landscape.

In this response paper, I discuss the process and structure of academic writing and how the choice of an English language variant and rules of punctuation affect academic essay writing. Further, I discuss the importance of style guides and avoiding plagiarism in academic essay writing.

2) ESSAY WRITING

This module is very beneficial as it has given me insights into how to better write academic essays. During my career, I found myself drafting various proposals and reports either about refugee protection matters or other related issues such as access to asylum in the East and Horn of Africa, and the Great Lakes region and issues of attainment of durable solutions for persons in need in line with the 1951 Refugee Convention and 1969 OAU convention, including other legislative frameworks. While leading teams, it became evident that understanding key concepts was vital. I concur with the fact that nearly all academic writing shares some kind of formal prose register, citations and references to other works, use of stable rhetorical moves to define the project's scope, position it in relevant research, and advance new contributions and that academic essays seek to provide answers to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence (EUCLID 2024, 7). This gives one a vision of the purpose of your essay.

The basic steps required when beginning essay writing are very beneficial. From analyzing the question and defining key terms, establishing points of view, researching the topic using credible academic sources, taking notes from your preliminary reading, developing your essay plan and organizing your ideas, drafting your essay into main parts (introduction, body, and conclusion), keeping the draft aside for 1-2 days then reviewing it and making changes, editing and redrafting the essay, having a colleague read it and complete or check references, and finally handing in the essay (EUCLID 2024, 8)

Had I known the above during my time at the UNHCR Regional Office as a Regional Protection Officer, covering the East and Horn and the Great Lakes region, where my work predominantly entailed drafting UNHCR's position papers on the situation within the region, legal briefs, situation analysis, and many other reports, this would have greatly enabled me to align my thought process. Often, I would quickly introduce the situation and sometimes spend more time delving into other issues that were not directly related to the subject matter before identifying a solution.

3) USE OF AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

From my reports, American English and British English were used interchangeably depending on the context. For my thesis, we were guided as it was based on a particular style of drafting; the first was APA, and the second was Oxford. I have also realized that the choice of spoken or written English is influenced by various factors such as the school one attended, the required drafting style, the consumers of the report's content, and the writer's country of origin.

Being Kenyan and having been colonized by the British, we currently have more British schools and children speaking British English, often ending up in British Universities. However, it is very evident that American English has grown steadily in international significance since World War II, parallel to the growth of U.S. political, economic, technological, and cultural influence worldwide (EUCLID 2024, 25).

4) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism refers to "using a source of information without giving credit to the author. Examples of plagiarism include taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet without giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism" (EUCLID 2024, 34). Therefore, it is essential to note that every source referred to during the literature review should be acknowledged and well-cited to do justice to the author's effort and maintain academic integrity (EUCLID 2024d, 34)

I first came to terms with the terms and importance of proper citation (in-text and listing cited sources) of the writer's work during my first Master of Arts Degree in Project Planning and Management. This ethical way of ensuring a writer's work is acknowledged by rephrasing, paraphrasing, quoting, and using visuals, among others, is very important, especially during academic essay writing and in our workplaces when drafting reports, essays, briefs, and other documents used to transfer knowledge or for the consumption of others.

From my observations, the complexity of citation lies in the style of referencing, as this is an area that I also struggle with. This is because it has to be in line with your drafting style, and without support from tools such as Zotero, it is often easy to include or exclude

very relevant information. Another aspect that is a good reminder when punctuating is when to use personal style and academic style of punctuation. Academic style means (among other things) using logical connectors so that there is flow in your papers (EUCLID 2024, 39).

In my daily work, I have realized that citations, in-text citations, punctuations, and paraphrases are often inaccurately used. For example, there are little and long quotations, and they have to be used accurately with the author's name being put in parentheses followed by the page number (EUCLID 2024, 39).

5) PUNCTUATION

Academic essay writing and even drafting of other papers for various reasons demand precise punctuations. This adds clarity to sentences. Academic essay writing is guided by rules to ensure writers' right communication of ideas. Punctuations and language variants are two important rules that guide effective and consistent academic essay writing. Punctuations convey meanings to sentences (EUCLID 2024f, 16). For example, the apostrophe conveys possession of singular nouns or indefinite pronouns. Apostrophes are also used to express contractions of two words in the English language. The bullet symbol is used in lists of words, phrases, or clauses that complete sentences. Depending on their position in a sentence, the colon and semicolon determine the meanings of parts of the sentence. While the semicolon links two related parts of a sentence, the colon connects unrelated parts. Commas have multiple usages, conveying meanings in sentences (EUCLID 2024, 19–20). They are used to identify non-defining clauses, words, or phrases according to their placement in sentences.

EUCLID (2024, 25) suggests that using a chosen language variant of the English language provides consistency and meaning in academic papers. The prominent variants are arguably the British and American variants (EUCLID 2024, 25). These two prominent variants may have different spellings of some words but the same pronunciation or vice versa. Further, some words may have the same spelling but may convey additional meanings when used in some contexts. Other differences include the usage of punctuation, collective nouns, and plural adjectives.

6) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide entails documenting your approach as an author to certain aspects of writing style that need to be consistent. For the finished publication to be coherent, a style guide is necessary. That is why certain types of writing, such as technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting, which relate to style guides, require a consistent writing style (EUCLID 2024, 41).

Guidelines ensure publishable work does not reflect a single author's style, allowing multiple authors to make their contributions. When written work lacks a single authoritative source on style, as it should, it prompts discussion on the elements of style. Style surpasses the correct and precise use of punctuation and grammar. Aspects of style include appropriate sentence lengths, structure, attention given to the subject, jargon, and preferred voice (EUCLID 2024, 41).

While freelancers can apply a recommended style, they have the opportunity to learn from their customers and use their feedback to improve service delivery. Hence, sustaining the customer as the preferred writer (EUCLID 2024, 42).

7) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the insights gained from the orientation documents, ACA-401D period one (1) course pack, and the instructional video by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck have underscored the significance of my Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Diplomacy and International Affairs (DDIA) program in my professional endeavors. This program promises to enhance my proficiency in academic essay writing and various document drafting, enabling me to communicate with clarity for a simplified read. Importantly, the acquired knowledge will not only benefit me personally but also empower me to mentor my staff, ensuring that they meet the expectations during report drafting and other tasks. I am confident that the skills and insights gained will prove invaluable in navigating the complexities of my role and making meaningful contributions to my field.

REFERENCES

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

UNHCR. 2012. "Dadaab - World's Biggest Refugee Camp 20 Years Old." Accessed April 2, 2024. <https://www.unhcr.org/news/stories/dadaab-worlds-biggest-refugee-camp-20-years-old#:~:text=More%20than%20463%2C000%20Somali%20refugees,Kenya%20originally%20intended%20for%2090%2C000.&text=UNHCR%20set%20up%20the%20first,host%20more%20than%20463%2C000%20refugees.>

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.